

How Did China Make the Transition to Green Mining?

The world has indeed become oriented towards green mining, and China has emerged in developing this field since 2003. Although mining technologies have made significant progress over the years due to the influence of industrial power, resource depletion and traditional mining have generated problems that are still severe in many developing countries. Nevertheless, the policy of green mining is a difficult choice for the Chinese government and the mining industry, and it is essential to have multiple disciplines cooperating. Introduction: The green mine has become a general plan for mining in China, which can enhance other related fields. According to Huang (2008), green mining is an evaluation index system for the base of green mines, relying on efficient use and cleaner production, in addition to unified management. Moreover, it provides practical suggestions and a comprehensive assessment using traditional Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). It is worth noting that the green mine is merely a method of mining and an important foundation in the scope of resource innovation and green development. Green mining is not entirely identical with green or sustainable development, which is often defined as 'development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs

Mineral resources

China's Mineral Resource Consumption Rates, Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China, 2022

Damages

The damages from mining are extensive, encompassing environmental, social, and even health impacts, as well as natural disasters. One of the visible issues is chemical damage.

Chemical pollution occurs in the following ways:

Heavy metal ions infiltrate groundwater, resulting in Acid Mine Drainage (AMD), which is caused by complex reactions between metals and oxygen according to the metal structures.

The discharge of acid mine drainage (AMD) during mining operations increases the acidity of surrounding rivers and lakes, significantly affecting the survival of aquatic organisms. In 2000, a study conducted by LeBlanc found that the Tinto River region in southwestern Spain was

heavily polluted due to mining activities. The Tinto River, locally known as the "Red River," is highly acidic and contaminated with metals (LeBlanc, M., Morales, J., Borrego, J., & Elbaz-Poulichet, F. (2000). Acid mine drainage impacts in the Tinto River, Spain. *Environmental Geology*, 39(11), 1104–1110). In 2019, the risks of acid and heavy metal pollution from mining activities on fish population decline were discussed; it was concluded that metal pollution and bioaccumulation from mining activities were the greatest threats to fish survival. This was not the only issue with traditional mining, as it is also harmful from a health perspective.

Health damages caused by exposure to toxic substances such as mercury, which led to neurological and digestive problems and the birth of deformed children. In 1997, the World Bank issued a report targeting China's industrial pollution control policy (World Bank, 1997. *China: Industrial Pollution Control Policy*. <https://www.worldbank.org>). The report stated that 'hundreds of thousands of cases of premature death and serious respiratory diseases resulted from exposure to polluted industrial air.'

1. According to the Chinese Ministry of Health, industrial pollution has made cancer the leading cause of death in China.
2. Ambient air pollution alone kills hundreds of thousands of citizens each year.
3. 500 million people in China have been deprived of access to clean and safe drinking water.

I. Main geological issues

- Drainage of mine pits
- Stock of solid waste
- Wastewater discharge
- Land destruction
- Avalanches, landslides, mudslides
- Ground subsidence

II. Main geological types and scale tables

	Small	medium	Large	None
	<1500 hm ²	1500~6000 hm ²	>6000 hm ²	None
	<2500×10 ⁴ m ³	(2500~8000)×10 ⁴ m ³	>8000×10 ⁴ m ³	None
	<2000×10 ⁴ t	(2000~8000)×10 ⁴ t	>8000×10 ⁴ t	None
	<2000×10 ⁴ m ³	(2000~8000)×10 ⁴ m ³	>8000×10 ⁴ m ³	None
	<2000 hm ²	(2000~10,000) hm ²	>10,000 hm ²	None

Processing Stage

Starting in 1998, control over industrial pollution began through the reform of regulatory policies, which included the closure of thousands of polluting mines.

The Eleventh Five-Year Plan 2006-2010

It aimed to reduce emissions by 10% due to the increase in sulfur dioxide (SO₂) emissions above 2005 levels. The gradual closure of small power plants with low fuel efficiency was implemented, along with the installation of sulfur removal devices such as Limestone-Gypsum Wet FGD and Seawater Flue Gas Desulfurization [eos]

	2005 mil. tons	mil. tons	Change from 2005	mil. tons	Change from 2005	Change from BAU
Power sector	13.3	18	+35%	10	-25%	-44%
All other sectors	12.2	13	+6%	13	+6%	0%
Total	25.5	31	+19%	23	-10%	-26%

Source: IES (2007)

Focusing on hydroelectric energy through the development and financing of numerous solar panels and wind power generators.

Employing natural treatments such as root-associated bacteria (PGPR), which enhance plant growth and also help plant roots resist stress, in addition to remediating pollutants by reducing the uptake of toxic elements by plants through converting metals like cadmium or lead into water-insoluble forms, thereby preventing their absorption.

The pace of intelligence transformation in China's mining sector has accelerated in recent years, with applications such as intelligent extraction, driverless operation, and underground 5G private networks. One of the most prominent examples is the Xinwen Coal Mine in Shanxi Province, affiliated with Lu'an Chemical. The mine relies on an underground 5G private network with transfer speeds exceeding gigabits per second to expand the range of intelligent applications. Wang Feng, an official at the Xinwen Coal Mine, stated that with the support of 5G technology and smart equipment, the mine is able to achieve accurate positioning of all employees and vehicles within just one second. He added that 128 AI-equipped cameras are deployed throughout the mine.

Pollution levels in China in 2021 recorded a 42% decrease compared to 2013, according to a source from the Ministry of Ecology and Environment of China (MEE).

<https://english.mee.gov.cn/Resources/Reports/soe/SOEE2019/202312/P020231206603419884030.pdf>

The main pollution indicators in 1990 were as follows: exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), with the population-weighted average exposure to PM_{2.5} being high, approximately 57.8 µg/m³. The major pollutants: the annual average concentrations of total suspended particles (TSP), SO₂, and NO_x were about 0.387, 0.0930, and 0.043 mg/m³, respectively. The Ministry of Environmental Protection issued a report in 2011 which revealed that about 10% of

agricultural land had significant issues with exceeding permissible levels of toxic metals as well as scarce toxic elements. A comprehensive national report was issued in April 2014, covering soil over an area of 6.3 million square kilometers over eight years from 2005 to 2013. Samples from 16.1% of the total soil samples across the country were found to be contaminated, and 19.4% of samples from arable land showed evidence of pollution.

Challenges Facing China

Green growth faces difficulties in the Northeast and Xinjiang due to low oxygen levels and technological gaps. Additionally, Belinda Shepp, a Chinese policy analyst at CREA, stated that it is unclear how strongly China is committed to its goals, despite leaders' assurances that the government always fulfills its climate promises. There is also the challenge of convincing investors to support green mining projects.

Comparison between green mining and traditional mining in terms of initial and operational costs:

Initial costs of green mining: It requires significant investments in developing and purchasing more efficient and environmentally friendly equipment, such as electric trucks, and sustainable infrastructure. In terms of operational costs, it offers greater long-term savings through energy efficiency and reduced consumption, as well as by lowering waste management costs, which can reduce the space needed for landfilling or storage. On the other hand, traditional mining has reasonable initial costs but comes with ongoing environmental consequences.

Summary:

Since China has a long history of mining, it has a direct correlation with pollution, which has caused up to 760,000 deaths according to the World Bank. Consequently, China adopted and significantly developed the concept of green mining using 5G technology and artificial intelligence, allowing 300 workers who previously worked underground to now work above ground at the Xinyuan mine. Pollution levels in China have decreased by 42% compared to 2013 due to collaborative efforts, yet global deaths from pollution continue to rise.

The research also examined the challenges China faced, including both initial and operational costs, as well as mining in Arab countries and the gradual normalization processes that have begun there.

Conversely, China's carbon emissions in 2000 were 3.4 billion metric tons, with unchecked growth until 2012. Mining began integrating smart technologies, alongside the structural closure of polluting mines and the incorporation of renewable energy. Notable emerging technologies

include artificial intelligence and automation. Emissions eventually stabilized between 11.5 and 12 metric tons, entering a phase of horizontal stabilization and gradual decline.

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